

PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF IMPROVING THE NATIONAL SYSTEM OF PERSONNEL TRAINING IN INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: the article describes the philosophical aspects of improving the national system of personnel training in innovative development. Also, scientific conclusions are given to the comments regarding the stability of society and the solution of socio-economic problems.

Key words: innovative development, market economy, innovation, scientific technology, futurology, higher education, democratic society

In the current period, the work of ensuring the sustainable development of society is closely related to issues such as achieving the intended socio-economic goals, ensuring the development of a well-rounded personality, and protecting young people from the negative processes occurring in the environment. Among these problems, the need to form and improve immunity that can protect against environmental crises, mass culture that negatively affects young people, and the attack of negative information is considered one of the main tasks. In particular, the solution to these tasks is directly related to the global changes and development trends taking place in the world, that is, the process of increasing the desire to live only for profit as a result of the deepening of the fundamentalism of market economy relations. Humanity chases after "progress" and constantly strives to ensure it. But it does not recognize that this action is causing the depletion of natural resources and leading to environmental crises. Also, it does not take into account that every person is a person, a symbol of value, a representative of spiritual culture, in some cases it denies the content of its social goals. Another peculiarity of this process is that education is seen as a mechanism that helps to become a subject that fulfills the requirements of the market economy, rather than fulfilling the function of ensuring the spiritual growth of each generation. In this regard, it should be noted that in the present period, efforts are being made to find suitable ways of social development, and in this process, the task of ensuring the adaptability of the society to these development mechanisms is gaining urgent importance. The concept of ensuring sustainable development of society occupies a special place in the framework of such relations, that is, among existing theoretical ideas, scientifically based ideas. Philosophers and representatives of other sciences promote this concept as the only scientific concept that brings humanity out of the crises and crises of the current era and directly provides the opportunity for regular development.

Any innovative activity serves to systematically change social life and the natural environment. In this regard, it should be noted that the changes of the environment by the practical activities of incon should be carried out in projects with scientific conclusions. In general, environmental scientists have regularly warned about the negative consequences of the damage caused to the environment as a result of the expansion of anthropogenic

activities. Accordingly, in developed countries, a new branch of scientific knowledge, "futurology", i.e., "the science of the future" has spread widely among the public, and preliminary conclusions about the development of scientific technology and the consequences of the revolution of scientific technology have appeared. In the current period, the concept of "innovation" has replaced the concept of scientific technology development, scientific technology revolution [1]. It should be noted that innovations are created by icons who have different worldviews and values, needs, wishes, needs, united by feelings of commonality in their activities in a certain context. Innovative activity of innovators is manifested in intensive, scientifically based innovative activity.

One of the unique strengths of innovative activity is that innovators should have knowledge of the general laws of the process related to the need to change the environment, the essence and strengths of the innovative process, and realize that their creative activity is directed to perfection, as in nature. Management of innovative processes in the context of scientific conclusions gives the icon the opportunity to form ideas for the near future, sometimes for several decades, in some cases for the long term. Icon regularly improves living conditions, at the same time, this situation finds its reflection in his psyche, he analyzes reality carefully, draws conclusions necessary for his work. In this process, icon is self-monitoring and self-managing. Icon differs from other animals, acocan, in these aspects and tries to answer the question of how to live with it.

In the new stage of development, the members of Uzbek society need to make full use of all the opportunities of the knowledge process available to them in order to find a solution for future affairs. It is clear from the above that in order to understand the content and nature of innovation, which is a complex phenomenon, based on socio-philosophical methodology, it is necessary to know its theoretical principles. Looking at the management of innovative processes in practice from a socio-philosophical point of view, it creates the need for a new, scientific approach to its nature, character, results, content.

Our country, which is a part of global development, is entering a new stage of development and is striving to become one of the leading countries, as well as trying to find a mechanism to ensure the active participation of every person in this process. In this process, they are looking for ways to improve technical, technological, economic and management mechanisms. In such conditions, first of all, it is necessary to form a person's attitude to reforms and a worldview aimed at ensuring their development process. At the same time, there is a task to ensure the adaptation of the members of the society, the separate institutions, especially the youth and future specialists, to the ongoing processes. The role of higher education in the solution of such tasks is growing, because the higher education process educates a new corps of personnel entering social life, prepares them as specialists and forms the basis of their socialization into society. Higher education creates professional skills in future specialists, improves their positive attitude to national and universal values.

Philosophical aspects of the problems included in the topic and the relevance of the research are determined by the fact that higher education as a separate social institution plays an important role in the solution of socio-economic problems at the current stage, and its ability to adapt to the reformation changes taking place in society. It should be noted that only education, higher education, which is considered an important part of it, provides the ability of a person to adapt to different stages of development of society.

As a result of education and upbringing of the new generation, the outlook, culture, and professional knowledge of young people and future specialists are formed, and directions for social development are created. These factors require in-depth scientific and philosophical study and research of higher education as a factor that ensures the stable development of society at the stage of new development.

Based on the fact that the new stage of development in Uzbekistan is a part of the development of human civilization and taking into account the processes that can negatively affect the development of society, it is of practical importance to analyze the role of higher education in these processes. That is why philosophers and sociologists in our country are studying the current content, goals and tasks of higher education, its place in the innovative development of society in various aspects. It should be noted that sociological researchers pay special attention to the role of higher education in the transition to the model of sustainable development of society, and at the same time describe the new model of higher education as the main factor that ensures sustainable development. It should be noted that although there are scientific researches devoted to the development of higher education and the essence of the concept of sustainable development in our country, there have been no systematic philosophical studies devoted to the fact that higher education is a factor that ensures and guarantees the sustainable development of the society during the new stage of development. In the present period, in researching the methodological functions of the philosophy of education, it is necessary to pay special attention to the fact that higher education is a factor that ensures the sustainable development of society. Also, studying the process of flexibility of the subjects of society in improving the constantly developing content of higher education is also an urgent problem. Especially from the point of view of the content of the positive changes taking place in the society, that is, there is a need to independently study the ontological features of higher education and its ability to adapt to these processes. Therefore, the priority importance of sustainable development in the development of society, the scientific justification of the adaptation of the processes taking place in society to it is one of the urgent scientific and philosophical problems. Determining the ontological and axiological characteristics of the development of the higher education system in the stable development of the society in the conditions of Uzbekistan is also of practical importance.

It should be noted that at the new stage of development, it is necessary to determine the ontological features of higher education, i.e., to provide future professionals with scientific justification of their intellectual capabilities in terms of the current global problems, effectively using the changes in the national mentality, worldview and culture of young people. The stable development of the country in the new era depends, first of all, on the improvement of social relations and the near future development of existing socio-economic relations in the society. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the sustainable development of society includes not only economic development based on innovation, but also indicators characteristic of radical changes in social life, spiritual culture, and external cultural relations.

There is a dialectical social cooperation in the interaction of the modern democratic society with the educational system, and therefore education appears as the cause and result of the processes taking place in the society. In general, higher education prepares and adapts society to natural and social changes. The main purpose of higher education as an adaptive system in relation to human, state and society relations is closely related. Understanding that higher education is an important value plays a key role in the formation of conditions of

flexibility for sustainable development in society and in the effective use of all its scientific and educational opportunities in this process.

The improving society of Uzbekistan is systematically searching for modern values at a new stage of development. In such conditions, the importance of a philosophical approach to the study of the subject increases, because only in the philosophical observation can one find scientifically based answers to the complexities put forward by the society. If a comparative conclusion is made with respect to the existing society in developed countries, it becomes clear that fundamental socio-economic changes in the country, that is, the concept of stabilization of society, can be implemented only on the basis of a scientific dialectical project. A special feature of the modern educational process in ensuring the flexibility of society is that the higher education process is manifested as a special value in practice.

The growing importance of the improved higher education system as a value is a direct reflection of the society's attempt to find a way to a new civilization, that is, a society capable of sustainable development. During the bold movement towards a sustainable society, the rise of the higher education process as a value is not lagging behind, but advancing from it, showing itself as a progressive system that meets the interests and demands of a steadily developing society and is able to absorb its socio-economic demands. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, higher education is one of the factors that can find its conceptual solutions as one of the tools that ensure the sustainable development of society. This goal is aimed at educating a competitive corps of personnel, preparing them for practice at the level of modern requirements, and forming a new worldview in the higher education system. The formation and growth of higher education as a value is compatible with the rapid and innovative development of society, and its main goal is to find a scientific solution to existing socio-economic problems and to take Uzbekistan's rightful place among developed countries, to increase the moral, political, and patriotic culture of young people, and together with this, society is to serve to ensure that its development is safe, ecologically stable.

It should be noted that the social importance of higher education is only pragmatic, i.e. teaching future specialists the knowledge characteristic of past times, not limited to the development of their professional skills, but also the formation of personal characteristics such as high intelligence, worldview, sense of responsibility, activity, creative activity typical of modern specialists. is considered As a result, this process serves rapidly developing social and economic relations.

The concept of sustainable development is the result of many years of scientific research of philosophers, sociologists, environmental scientists, and is aimed at finding a systematic solution to socio-economic problems, preventing environmental crises from happening in society. A sustainable developed society is a system aimed at the improvement of social relations in all aspects, including economic, political management, culture, education, spirituality and other areas, at the same time, it requires the mutual harmony of human and social relations. In such conditions, the concept of sustainable development, with its compatibility with human interests and social orientation, preserves social and cultural diversity in the future, serves for their systematic improvement.

The new stage of development of the society is characterized by the deepening of reforms in the field of socio-economic and management, and in this process, increased attention to the human factor. Such a situation created the need for specialists who graduated from higher educational institutions to have high qualifications, to be ready for self-

management, to be able to solve the tasks promoted by socio-economic development, and to receive continuous education throughout their life, and to systematically improve their qualifications. In this regard, higher education is recognized as a factor that ensures the sustainable development of society and its security. That is why new goals and tasks are being set for higher education, the attitude towards higher education policy has changed during the reforms.

The need for specialists who have graduated from higher educational institutions to have high qualifications is specifically noted in the state educational standards and is one of the priority tasks of modernization of higher education in the new era. Such a new, innovative approach to the training of qualified specialists is one of the important directions in the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2021 [2]. A scientifically based, qualified approach is needed to solve this problem.

In the process of higher education, the main goal is to educate a person who can think freely, who can act on the basis of humanism and justice, and who has versatile skills. Specialists with the above characteristics have the ability to solve social and professional tasks encountered in everyday life. The innovative approach to higher education is fundamentally different from the method of acquiring knowledge based on the plan, which has been a priority in the training of specialists until now. A modern approach to the formation of the professional skills of specialists, i.e., its content, technologies, and methods, is a factor of improving the renewed higher education and a method of educating bachelors and masters suitable for the new era. In this process, it is necessary for higher education to fulfill its task of forming humanistic, spiritual and moral qualities in future specialists. It should be noted that this process is closely related to factors such as accelerating socio-economic development and changes in human working conditions.

In the present era, when the relations of the market economy are deepening, innovations are proving to be a necessary process in the training and education of specialists. Also, the positive changes taking place in the environment and social systems, that is, their impact on higher education, are increasing the practical importance of innovations. The concept of innovation first appeared in the scientific research works of foreign sociologists in the 20th century and was used in the sense of the influence and penetration of some elements characteristic of one culture into another culture [3].

The term innovation is derived from the Latin word "innovatia", which means renewal, change. It can be understood in terms of renewal, improvement. In general terms, it is a special cultural value, i.e., its material and immaterial appearance, and innovation is recognized as something new by man at the present time. It should be noted that according to researcher S.N.Kreytor, "Innovation is the process of using knowledge to ensure technological, competitiveness and leadership". The analysis of the scientific literature on the content and nature of innovations shows that the application of this term to higher education is the improvement of the pedagogical process, the renewal of educational services, the introduction of new technologies into educational products, the introduction of scientific achievements, the perfection of the higher education process as an objective process [4].

Humanity facing development is currently trying to form a single social system with favorable living and working opportunities for people. The role of innovation in solving such a common, global social integration task is growing. The idea of the need to create a new social situation, that is, an innovative world, is being promoted by leading sociologists in the world.

In this process, it is necessary to effectively use the possibilities of rapidly developing computer equipment and communication technologies. In this regard, it should be noted that one of the distinctive features of the current era is the innovative changes being introduced to the social and economic aspects on a large scale. Innovations are of great practical importance for Uzbekistan, which is increasingly deeply integrated into the world community. The use of innovations in all systems of society, including higher education, forms the possibility of integration with the current era and globalizing world processes, and the realization of positive directions of development.

The deepening of market relations has created new forms of higher education, an increasingly perfect system. In this process, higher education is acting as a strategic resource of the country's development, and higher education institutions were formed as a system that responds to the positive changes taking place in society immediately, based on effective methods and scientific conclusions.

In the course of the unique development of higher education in the new stage of development, the volume of scientific and methodological works has expanded due to the introduction of new goals and developments, improved topics and technologies into the content of higher education. This situation suggests the need to widely use new methods in the pedagogical process in higher educational institutions. In the current development of higher education, the importance of theoretically based, goal-oriented, practical pedagogical innovations is increasing. At the current stage of development of our country, pedagogical innovations have a direct impact on all aspects of higher education. Also, taking into account the unique characteristics of each higher educational institution, it is causing positive changes in the content of educational, methodological and scientific research, educational work. For example, in our country, "In the last two years, 1551 scientific works were defended and the scientific potential was increased to 36.7% (32.7% in 2017)", through the "El-yurt umidi" fund, in 2019, training abroad, internship, master's degree and 517 professors and staff were selected for doctoral studies, and 218 were sent abroad to date" [5].

Innovations are also reflected in the content of subjects taught in higher education institutions, newly established pedagogical technologies applied to the educational process, and modern forms and methods of training future specialists. The analysis shows that the accumulation of innovations in the structure of higher education leads to the emergence of new systems in socio-economic life, the expansion of opportunities for modern education of future specialists. This process depends on the human factor and is reflected in the positive changes taking place in the socio-economic systems of society. Innovations are the emergence of new things in the process of higher education due to human activity, their practical use, full satisfaction of the requirements of the market of educational services, their advantage, complexity and specific features compared to the innovations that have existed until now.

Innovations are manifested in the process of effective use of innovations or their mutual exchange at various levels of higher education institutions. Innovations in higher education are used in the process of implementation of newly created joint faculties, established departments, and improved educational programs as a result of the activities of professors and teachers. At the same time, innovation is also embodied as a specific form of effective use in educational services and systems in the ever-expanding social life.

The main tasks of innovations in higher education institutions include the following: firstly, innovations are the result of scientific work carried out by professors and teachers,

they realize the intellectualization of activity, strengthen the scientificity of lectures, practical training, and the possibilities of connection with practice. Increases students' interest in acquiring their future specialty; secondly, as a result of scientific research, innovations create a basis for quality implementation of projects of a scientific, practical and fundamental nature, which are carried out with the participation of economic contracts, professors and teachers, doctoral students and independent researchers; thirdly, innovation plays an important role in the systematic improvement of educational services. Also, thanks to innovations, the latest news will be included in the content of monographs, textbooks and training manuals, scientific articles prepared for publication by professors and teachers.

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